

ISic0626

I.Sicily inscription 0626

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble (white)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Trapani, Museo Regionale

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR072109

1. Pompeianis vita.
2. Ob insignem iustitiam
3. et merita litterarum et amorem
4. quem non solum circa patriam
5. sed per omnem provinciâ conlocavit,
6. Iul (io) Cl (audio) Peristerio
7. Pompeiano, v (iro) c (larissimo) , ex cons (ulari) p (rovinciae) S (iciliae) ,
8. universa curia in coetu splendido splendido suo
9. patrono digno et prestantissimo praestantissimo ,
10. statuam conlocavit.
11. Amazoniis vita.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284556

EDR 072109

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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